

HORIZON-EIC-2022-PATHFINDEROPEN-01**PERSEUS**

**2D Material-Based Multiple Oncotherapy
Against Metastatic Disease Using a
Radically New Computed Tomography
Approach**

DELIVERABLE

WP5 – D5.4 – Graphic assets

ABSTRACT

The document outlines the production of print and presentation materials for the dissemination of Perseus.

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Disclaimer

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a short overview of the production of all print and presentation materials that will be used for the communication and dissemination of PERSEUS. All future graphic materials for PERSEUS will be based on the designs and templates described in this document. Graphic materials play a key role in dissemination and communication, as the first impression one gets of the project, which cannot be undone, is imparted by them.

2 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document features 7 chapters.

Chapters 1 and 2 are a short introduction. Chapter 3 specifies who will use the designs and this deliverable. Chapter 4 provides a brief overview of the philosophy behind the design of the dissemination materials. Chapter 5 provides a list of the designs that were produced and details how the design and copywriting process unfolded. Chapter 6 provides low-resolution copies of the above designs. Chapter 7 sums up the conclusions and take-home messages that were gleaned through this work.

3 INTRODUCTION - WHO WILL BE USING THESE DESIGNS AND THIS DELIVERABLE?

Graphic assets include designs that will be printed (print materials) and designs which will be used exclusively for online communication. They are part of the dissemination and communication materials - tools of PERSEUS and will be used by:

- All partners
- All WP leaders
- Particularly by the staff responsible for each institution's communication activities.

In addition, as this is a public document and is available on the project's website, it will be accessible by external parties interested in disseminating and communicating PERSEUS.

This deliverable will be updated periodically according to the project's needs. A second release is due at M32.

4 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

The design of the graphic materials was based on two simple but effective requirements: starting from the existing project logo, and tweaking the project website if necessary, we aimed to design a suite of graphic materials that is at the same time *distinctive* and *classic*. Achieving both a degree of timelessness and a striking design that 'speaks to everyone' has in turn two significant consequences. A timeless and classic look means that the design is conceived to 'age well'.

On the other hand, a strong graphic statement that is simple, easy to identify, and based on universal proportions (such as for instance certain mathematical ratios) allows the use of the same design/theme for both dissemination and communication. This strong visual identity was consistently 'declined' in the various print designs.

Both considerations translate into cost and labour savings for the project, especially with a view to its future upkeep/sustainability.

Another cost-saving consideration was the idea of designing templates for brochures and posters that the partners will be able to easily fill in and print locally as the need arises (see below).

5 LIST OF THE GRAPHIC ASSETS THAT WERE PRODUCED

In terms of graphic materials for dissemination and communication, the needs of such an ambitious project as PERSEUS are many. Broadly speaking, some printed assets are meant to be general-purpose, i.e. deployable anywhere without any changes, whilst others are event-specific, i.e. tailored to each specific PERSEUS International Workshop, of which three are planned, or event.

All print designs were conceived so as to be easily printable via standard CMYK offset printing. The colour palette was chosen so that the gamut coincided in both CMYK and RGB versions of the designs, so that small runs of digital prints would feature the same vibrant colours, thus guaranteeing value for money. The same logic was followed for the choice of the print formats, which for paper media are all standard ISO 216 / DIN formats. Using standard ISO 216 / DIN formats instead of more 'fashionable' ones translates into savings for the project and in no way diminishes the impact of the designs.

Based on the project schedule as well as on an evaluation of the overall progress so far, the following assets were thus identified and then designed:

1. three-fold general-purpose A4 Project brochure;
2. template for Workshop/event-specific A2 Project poster;
3. general-purpose 80x200 Project vinyl banner;
4. general-purpose PERSEUS-branded Project tote bag;
5. general-purpose PERSEUS-branded Project lapel pin;
6. template for PERSEUS slides;
7. social media icons & banners.

1) General-purpose foldable A4 brochure, to be deployed at various events as a general presentation of the project. The brochure features a concise but informative text introducing PERSEUS, a list of the partners, contact details, as well as the acknowledgement of EU and UKRI funding.

2) Workshop poster design: vertical A2 poster, printable as A3 if necessary. A larger format guarantees greater visibility, so A2 was chosen because it is the largest possible DIN format that can be hung without too much trouble in pinboards and public spaces. The design is compatible with printing in A3, which is significantly cheaper for small runs of digital prints.

3) General-purpose 80x200 standalone vinyl banner, to advertise and signal PERSEUS' presence during large events taking place in a specific venue, such as conferences, seminars, lectures, press conferences, etc. but also in-person EC events. The choice of PVC as the printing material makes the roll-up banner suitable for outdoor use as well.

4) General-purpose PERSEUS-branded tote bag, to be given to all Workshop participants, as well as to guests, as part of the welcome pack.

5) General-purpose PERSEUS-branded lapel pin, to be used during online meetings between the PERSEUS Consortium and the EC and/or with external actors, such as prospective investors; pins could also be given to Workshop participants as well as to guests, if Partners so wish.

6) Template for PERSEUS slide presentations. To be used by all partners when presenting on behalf of PERSEUS. A set of coherent graphic rules to customise the slides is provided.

7) Social media icons & banners were derived from one of the leitmotifs and optimised according to the various social media guidelines.

Insofar as possible, PERSEUS designs will be printed locally by partners, close to where they are meant to be deployed, in order to avoid the expense and environmental impact of shipping. The designs are sent to partners with specific instructions as to the type of printing process, paper, and finish to be adopted, so as to ensure a consistently high standard of quality.

All the designs were optimised for offset printing but can be output as high-quality laser or inkjet prints if necessary.

5.1 The actual design process

Work on the designs for PERSEUS's printed materials was conceived to evolve based on the graphic design done previously for the project: from the outset, we sought to expand as a coherent whole the system of typesetting and design rules underlying the project's graphic identity.

So the starting point was the project logo (see D5.3 Project Logo). We sought initially to complement the forms of inorganic chemistry evoked by the straight lines and angular points of the logo with the rounded lines of organic chemistry. As it is customary for QED, for this organic-vs-inorganic juxtaposition we drew inspiration from actual scientific research - a striking image of cell growth over inorganic pillars - taken from one of the posters at CNR-IMEM in Parma:

*The inspiration for the organic-vs-inorganic juxtaposition came from an image of human cells growing over an inorganic substrate. From Ghezzi et al., Sub-Micropillar Spacing Modulates the Spatial Arrangement of Mouse MC3T3-E1 Osteoblastic Cells, *Nanomaterials*, Vol. 9, Iss. 12, 1701 (2019); doi:10.3390/nano9121701*

The rounded pattern representing organic chemistry was then designed to be evocative of liposomes, one of the key structures at the heart of PERSEUS:

The rounded pattern is designed so as to evoke the shape of liposomes

We soon realised that the further ‘structuring’ of the pattern and the repetition of the ‘module’ thus obtained lent themselves to the creation of interesting textures, useful for a variety of designs:

Textures for the designs are obtained by further structuring of the liposome leitmotiv

At this stage, nearly all the building blocks for the design were in place. We proceeded to use them to produce the various assets.

Finally, for the icons for social media, rather than the capital P from the Logo, we elected to use the same liposome-like pattern:

The process of construction of the icons for social media profiles

The rounded crop given by the icon naturally evoked an image as viewed through the loupe of a microscope. We thus decided to incorporate this image in the designs as well. The final designs can be seen in Chapter 6.

5.2 Copywriting

Similar considerations of simplicity and efficacy were adopted for the copywriting. The latter eschewed lingo as much as possible in favour of clear and simple explanations, understandable by the general public, but also providing meaningful information for specialists.

6 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS

Foldable general-purpose Project brochure

Template for event-specific A2 Project poster

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General-purpose 80x200 Project vinyl banner

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General-purpose PERSEUS-branded Project tote bag

General-purpose PERSEUS-branded Project lapel pin

Title 02 Chart

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Chart Title

Category	Series 1	Series 2	Series 3
Category 1	2.5	3.8	1.3
Category 2	3.8	2.5	1.3
Category 3	1.3	3.8	2.5
Category 4	2.5	3.8	1.3

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Title 03 Images

Image 01 - Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.

Image 02 - Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.

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Title 03 Table

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Value 1	Value 2	Value 3	Value 4	Value 5	Value 6
001	A	1	001	A	U
002	B	2	002	D	8
003	C	3	003	F	8
004	D	4	004	G	J
005	E	5	005	H	O

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Team

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Template for PERSEUS slides - examples

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PERSEUS social media icons

Next page: PERSEUS social media banners

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7 CONCLUSIONS

We think the results show the benefit of involving a professional media production company with the right profile in the design and copywriting process.

The Consortium now has general-purpose brochures, posters, stand-alone banners, pins, and tote bags ready for any event.

Partners now have the templates at their disposal, so that they can start planning the printing of their own posters and brochures.

The designs are now finalised, but will continue to evolve organically in response to the changing needs of the Project. In particular, suitable 'buffer time' will need to be scheduled before the delivery of the printed materials. This is in order to take into account possible small changes due to event-specific needs. Further suitable buffer time should be factored in for checking printed samples ahead of each print run: the correct rendition of text, logos, and graphics/colours should be checked, as well as the quality of the folding in the case of the brochures.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche	Italy (Coordinator)	CNR
Karolinska Institutet	Sweden	KI
Technion - Israel Institute Of Technology	Israel	TECHNION
Universidad De Vigo	Spain	UVIGO
Wigner Fizikai Kutatokozpont	Hungary	Wigner RCP
BeDimensional Spa	Italy	BeD
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL